

Chalcones XXII : Studies on Heterocyclic Chalcone Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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Manuscript received 22 March 1977, revised 5 November 1977,
accepted 1 February 1978

THE use of aryl styryl heterocyclic ketones is almost unknown in the field of coordination chemistry.

However, attempts have been made¹⁻⁵ to employ 2'-hydroxy chalcones as analytical reagents and to

ratio method and confirmed by their molecular formula. Magnetic measurements were carried out at 30° using Gouy's method; μ_{eff} values of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes were found to be 1.83 and 2.01 B.M., respectively. Infrared spectra of ligand and the metal complexes were recorded in nujol mull using Beckmann spectrophotometer. Bands at 480 and 495 Cm^{-1} (Cu(II) complex) and 523 and 465 Cm^{-1} (Ni(II) complex) are indicative of metal to nitrogen and metal to oxygen linkage. No such bands were observed in the HQC spectrum. Stretching frequency of the (-OH) and (C-N) linkage at 3250 and 1665 Cm^{-1} , respectively, in the free ligand were shifted to lower values in the spectra of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes (indicative of M-N and M-O bond formation) as observed by Poddar and Das¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to UGC for financial assistance, Dr. S. K. Sinha, Principal, F.G. College, Raebareli for providing facilities and Director, CDRI Lucknow, for analytical work.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, MAGNETIC DATA AND IR BANDS OF COMPLEXES

Complex (Molecular formula)	Colour	% Metal		% Nitrogen		μ_{eff} B. M.	M—O M—N Cm^{-1}
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N) ₂	Bluish green	10.51	10.38	4.19	4.57	1.83	495
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N) ₂	Yellowish green	9.87	9.22	5.21	4.63	2.01	480 523

prepare complexes with some metal cations. Besides, the manifold biochemical activities⁶⁻⁸ of quinoliny chalcones and their coordinating nature with various cations is important. In the present communication, complexes have been isolated by treating 8-hydroxy-5-quinoliny chalcone (HQC) with Cu(II) and Ni(II) in 90% (aq.) Methanol. The isolated complexes were characterised conductometrically, spectrophotometrically and by magnetic measurements.

All the reagents used were of A.R. and G.R. grade. Spectrophotometric studies were carried out using Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20. The ligand, 8-hydroxy-5-quinoliny chalcone (HQC), was prepared as reported⁶ and its homogeneity was checked by employing TLC⁹. The complexes were prepared by adding HQC solution (2 mole) to a hot aq. methanolic solution of metal chloride (1 mole). The resulting solution was refluxed for 3 hours, cooled, filtered and washed several times with cold alcohol to get the crystalline material. Bluish green Cu(II) complex and yellowish green Ni(II) complex was crystallised from dioxan.

Conductometric titrations gave the stoichiometric ratio of the ligand to metal as 2 : 1. Molar composition of the complex was determined further by the molar

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